

Maturity Model in Process Mining as an Analytic Capability

This **maturity model**'s purpose is to evaluate the performance of company in using process mining as an analytic capability. The model consists of **7 dimensions** (see Figure 1) with 4 dimensions capturing management aspects and 3 dimensions capturing the Information Technology aspects. To make visualization easier, blue shades will represent the dimensions of the management side, and orange shades will represent the dimensions of the IT side.

Besides the dimensions, the model considers sub-dimension capabilities (see Table 1). Each sub-dimensional capability is associated with a level of implementation maturity. Six dimensions use the 5 maturity levels represented in the Capability Maturity Model Integration (CMMI). Based on our preliminary study, one dimension (Technology) uses 4 levels defined specifically based on the process mining academic literature.

Figure 1. Maturity Model Process Mining as Analytic Capability Structures

Table 1. Focus Area, Capability and Sub Dimension of the Preliminary Maturity Model

Focus Area	Capability	Level	Sub Dimension
Technology	Assess the information capability and analytic process in process mining	4 levels	Information Capability Analytic Process
Data	Assess the state and availability of data for process mining as an analytic capability as well as the associated data security and data quality policies and standards	5 levels	Data Availability Data Security Data Quality
Pipeline	Assess the state of PM workflow automated (from data gathering to their analysis and diffusion of the results) and how the data are gathered to be integrated and transformed into an event log that can be used for the workflow.	5 levels	Tooling Integration with Data Source Integration with Operational Application

Focus Area	Capability	Level	Sub Dimension
Strategic Alignment	Assess the strategy that examines the plan of action and roadmap support of process mining as an analytic capability	5 levels	Strategy Budgeting Business Contribution
Governance	Assess how an organization sets the formal rules and structures, including their documentation, regarding process mining as an analytical capability	5 levels	Communication Quality Metric Documentation System and Compliance Check
Culture	Assess the collective values shaping the attitude and behavior when human resources use process mining as analytical capability in their job	5 levels	Use Case Availability Management Involvement Customer Orientation Consistency
People	Assess how the human resources are managed in the organization to support process mining as an analytic capability	5 levels	Skill Responsibility

Based on the case study, we will measure their performance using our preliminary maturity model.

Case Study A – Telecom Company

Telecom Company is one of the top telecommunication companies in Southeast Asia. As mentioned in their mission, to orchestrate a digital ecosystem to deliver superior customer experience, they developed a particular unit responsible for managing Data, Systems, and Innovation in all Telecom Group companies (the DSI Unit). This unit organizes and oversees the provisioning of every customer-facing service and aims at combining data from different processes to analyze the customer-facing services and improve them over time.

They started a process mining project three years ago and succeeded in connecting all the information systems from multiple departments to obtain reliable data about service provisioning. This project then focused on Purchase-to-Pay and Sales-to-Activation. One of the main challenges faced was to manage the amount of data to eliminate execution gaps and inefficiencies. Some of the problems they have at the beginning of their problem are:

- Duplicate payments to vendors.
- Approval chain that takes employees wasted time.
- Delivery date accuracy caused penalties.
- Complaint from customer about product activation that led to new product delivery.
- Business decisions that are based on subjective experiences not data.

This project combines the finance, reporting, procurement, and human resource functions to deliver highly digitized data needed for process mining implementation. Two examples of outcomes from the analysis result are decreased approval time for purchase request in the approval chain. The second one is improving malfunction clearance that overcomes the malfunction of the company tools that are used by the customer to such degree that they replace less tools.

Their newest innovation was that they developed an action engine that can trigger concrete action based on the analysis finding of process mining. This action engine gets the data directly from the other application, displays it on a dashboard and predicts the next event for all ongoing cases. It also can predict KPI performance and automatically initiate corrective action when things go wrong. Two concrete examples are, they use alerts in logistics to better identify overdue deliveries from the supplier. In sales to activation, they accelerate customer with fixed networks. Action engine alerts help to deliver the connection time that promised to the customer.

Telecom Company is certified ISO9001:2015, which makes all the documentation manageable and reviewed annually with internal and external audits. The DSI Unit strategies ensure all information is secured and reported regular. They have a meeting scheduled every three months with all departments that gather new progress from previous AI projects and try to define added information that can be developed for new process mining use cases.

The application of the maturity model for process mining as an analytical capability to Telecom Company is shown below. The shades for each sub-capability represent the level associated with each sub-capability. For instance, Telecom Company level is “Defined” for the sub-capability (People-Skills). Since the limitation of the case study is to describe all the conditions of the company, darker blue shades will be used to show that the level comes from the statement in the case study and lighter shades will show that the levels were assumed. These light and darker shades also apply for the orange dimension, data, pipeline, and technology.

Dimension	Sub Dimension	PM Initiated	Diagnostic and Descriptive	Predictive	Prescriptive
TECHNOLOGY	Information Capability	Get process map visualizations, deliver simple insight about process in the organizations	Get insight into the event logs history, root cause analysis might be helpful to understand the reason and suggest for some core business process Analysis result is linked to value stream SLAs/KPI's using dashboard	Process mining result have predictive capability, using it for alerts and forecasting The dashboard gives some value with SLA/KPI's that align with business strategy	The recommendation gives information about what, when, and why an event or trend might happen and tells what actions have the highest potential for the best outcome. It allows the decision to fix problems, improve performance, or gives some valuable opportunities
	Analytic Process	Doing process discovery and conformance checking In some area of organizations	Simple analytic with diagnostic and descriptive capability, AI might be detected	Doing prediction using AI to the business use case to give some recommendation and supports daily process management across different department	Learn from historical, prediction and implementation result to triggers situationally aware automations or giving valuable actions needed for the ongoing system

Dimension	Sub Dimension	Initial	Managed	Defined	Quantitatively Managed	Optimized
PIPELINE	Tooling	Use a free commercial tool or develop apps from open source tools to do limited capabilities of process mining function	Use a commercial tool or develop the apps with advanced capabilities, need to pay or need to define specific business use case	Use a commercial tool or develop apps and using data that connected with ongoing process also generate the dashboard for visualization	Use commercial tool or develop apps, use the data from ongoing system, visualize it and give prediction or alert to fulfill certain KPI	Develop integrated platform with ongoing system (full commercial tools or customize with own code), make prediction and prescriptive alert also authorize automated action needed
	Integration with Data Source	Data sources need to be downloaded and adjusted to the process mining needs	Data sources was standardized to fulfill process mining needs, having initial plan for automated data sources integration with process mining module	Get the integration with the data source and create ongoing dashboard	Ongoing dashboard can show the prediction and make recommendation	Get the most up to date of existing data for latest predictive or prescriptive technique, data history 'learning' may support actionable decision

Dimension	Sub Dimension	Initial	Managed	Defined	Quantitatively Managed	Optimized
	Integration with Operational Applications	Independent PM process, not connected with operational application	Define which operational application that can relate to process mining plan, connect the data needed with other department/ business functional	Use PM experiments to build support for breaking down data silos and consolidating data for core business case	Ongoing dashboards connect with operational application and make suggestion for ongoing system	The process mining function connect all needed operational application throughout organization

Dimension	Sub Dimension	Initial	Managed	Defined	Quantitatively Managed	Optimized
DATA	Data Availability	Recognize relevant data for process mining	Pay attention to data acquisition standards for process mining	Propose data acquisition standards for the core business units	Establish data acquisition standard across multiple departments	optimize smart data acquisition across all industrial processes within departments of the enterprises
	Data Security	Have data security plan for PM implementation but no clear execution documented in the field	Pay general attention to data security execution and documentation for PM implementation	Make standardized documentation, execution, and performance measurement to deal with data security management for core business units	Implement data security management and monitoring across different departments and pay particular attention cyber security technology	Optimize data security management and practices across targeted business processes of the firm to eliminate any potential cyber risks in security management environment
	Data Quality	Identify the need of data quality for business process	Pay attention to dealing with data quality problems for process mining	Standardize data quality and solve compatibility problems for PM implementation in core business process	Standardize data cleansing and consolidation across the organization / multiple departments	optimize data quality across targeted industrial processes within departments of the enterprises

Dimension	Sub Dimension	Initial	Managed	Defined	Quantitatively Managed	Optimized
STRATEGIC ALIGNMENT	Strategy	Align business and technical leaders on the need for Process Mining Awareness	Use PM Proofs of Concept (POCs) to align leadership on PM investment	Define PM strategy and communicate to the organization, Gain budget and sponsorship for PM Project	Align PM strategy with other organizational roadmaps	Sustain momentum to keep innovating and transforming
	Budgeting	No PM Strategy, No PM Budgets	Short Term Strategy, but no dedicated PM budgets yet,	Medium Term PM Strategy and Dedicated PM Budgets	Dedicated PM Budgets	Long Term PM Strategy Dedicated PM Budgets
	Business Contribution	No Measure for Business Contribution	There will be measurement in Business contribution	Define the number for business Contribution	Giving a monitoring status for business contribution	Using business contribution for PM in the Quality Management System as KPI

Dimension	Sub Dimension	Initial	Managed	Defined	Quantitatively Managed	Optimized
GOVERNANCE	Communication	Understand the consequence and Challenge with PM Plan	Involve different stakeholders to gain a complete view of challenges and opportunities	Synthesize PM Plan to Practice and Guidance	Build organizational structures to manage the strength and scalability of PM	Engage with the PM Community to compare achievement
	Quality Metric	Identify PM Implementation in the roadmap	Translate principles into concrete responsibilities, processes, and metrics	Standardize governance practices with supporting technology such as reporting tools	Standardize governance practices, formulate insight from the data to the Corrective Action	Standardized governance practice, formulate insight from the data to the Preventive Plan
	Documentation System and Compliance Check	No Operating Procedure Established	SOP Established but Not Fully Implemented	SOP Implemented and Monitoring Documented, KPI defined	SOP Implemented, Monitoring Documented, KPI Recorded and measured	Use the Feedback from Monitoring and KPI for Continuous Improvement

Dimension	Sub Dimension	Initial	Managed	Defined	Quantitatively Managed	Optimized
CULTURE	Use Case Availability	See the Business Case Urgency but not yet fully managed for Process Mining	See the Business Case Urgency, make pilot project use case, define the method to apply PM	Connect with Other Department to Develop Solution, Use Case in Specific Business Case	Make Standardized Procedure and Integrate in the System to define and develop use case	Create Quality Management Cycle for All PM initiatives Process (PDCA)
	Management involvement	Rely on individual for change and problems in Process Mining Project	Have initiatives per department but lack of cooperation in PM implementation	Have cooperation and communication with another department for PM implementation	Have business and IT align for PM implementation and integration	Executive level sponsorship and integration in corporate strategy for PM
	Customer orientation	PM initiatives is a reaction from customer problem on the field (based on the case)	Start to have customer focus plan, accept customer sound to develop PM use case	Define the standard, procedure based on customer need from PM result	Have measurement for customer need and satisfaction to the business process	Customer focus strategy, customer insight data as input and optimize it based on measurement result
	Consistency	No consistency among the process business management in PM initiatives	Recognize the business process and the change needed for PM initiatives	Define the procedure for change management in PM cycle	Have the mechanism to measure and review the change management in PM cycle	Have optimized step to do continuous improvement or agreement in PM initiatives

Dimension	Sub Dimension	Initial	Managed	Defined	Quantitatively Managed	Optimized
PEOPLE	Skill	Basic Understanding of Process Mining Workflow Available, trial on new knowledge	Ability to perform of Process Mining Workflow Available	Ability to performs data analysis and decision making, understand the use of AI	Ability to perform complex analysis in Process Mining, may use AI in practice	Trained in Process Mining integrate with AI and empower other people
	Responsibility	Getting help from Process Mining specialist to identify dan solve knowledge gap	Form Ad Hoc team to identify the need of process mining implementation	Connect PM team with cross functional business process	Identify PM team with structure and responsibilities	Empower talent strategy for new skills and roles required for process mining

Case Study B – Fruitco Corporation

Fruitco Corporation is an Indonesian company that produces various products based on pineapple that is exported to South Asia countries. They manage the product from the pineapple plantation to the final delivery, aiming at achieving zero waste. Their mission is to ensure the delivery of the freshest and superior quality fruits all over Southern Asia.

They use ERP to manage all the operational data, like inventory, financial, accounting, manufacturing, and human resources. As one of the new improvements in their company, they want to transform their Order-to-Cash process and need insight from ERP data to plan relevant improvement activities. To support this idea, they created a project to get an end-to-end process analysis from ERP. The goal was to improve customer satisfaction through better delivery accuracy, production efficiency, optimized stock rotation and reduced production process changes.

As for a start, they decide to build one ad hoc team to do it. They equipped the team with capable people like data scientists, process mining analysts, data engineers, and software engineers. Only the head of the project team is the company's permanent staff, while the others have been hired on a temporary contract. The top management makes sure each head of department understands that they must work together with the team to ensure the success of the process mining initiative.

After 6 months and many meetings, the team defined a business process model and conducted a conformance checking analysis for the production and delivery of one of their top-selling products (sliced pineapple in a can), using the data collected from the ERP during the previous 6 months. Most of the delivery accuracy problems come from the production's steps. They analyze the process started with the order process from the customer then connected with the manufacturing process. There were raw materials delivered by hundreds of trucks daily. This process must have a good relationship with the plantation data to make sure harvest time and plant rotation. Process mining results give insight on stock reception and inventory transactions that are very crucial for manufacturing.

Even though the top management already had a commitment to carry out the mining process project, various technical obstacles arose in the field. Several times, the team faced reluctance from several departments to provide data and problems regarding data sources that needed further processing, such as data from plantations, which had different information systems. The team uses commercial process mining tools to analyze the event log data downloaded from the information system used in the company. As the final state of the team result, they succeeded in grouping orders that have a good delivery rate based on the season and the results of a particular plantation. Several anomalies are also seen related to the number of product stocks in the warehouse.

Using the same method, our model measures the performance of Case Study B. The cell with the color shows the level that achieved by the company. The cell with the color shows the level achieved by the company. Since the limitation of the case study is to describe all the conditions of the company, darker blue shades will be used to show that the level comes from the statement in the case study and lighter shades will show that the levels were assumed. These light and darker shades also apply for the orange dimension, data, pipeline, and technology.

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From our measurements, our maturity model can visualize both company measurements as shown in Figure 2. This measurement is based on six dimensions that have five levels, as for technology it was shown in Figure 3.

Maturity Model Measurement for PM as an Analytic Capability

Figure 2. Maturity Measurement Result for Dimensions with five levels

Figure 3. Maturity Measurement Result for Dimension with Four Levels